

Results of the ZKI Top Trends Survey of the ZKI Strategy and Organisation Working Group for 2021

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Introduction

The Strategy and Organisation working group of the ZKI Association conducts an annual survey on the most important topics and focal points of member institutions. The survey takes up and documents the most important issues of IT facilities from universities and research institutions in an annual instalment. In 2021, the survey focuses on the impact of the pandemic on IT institutions. It is completed by CIOs, heads of data centres, IT directors and persons in comparable roles. All responses are optional. The survey results from 2020 are prepared at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666167>.

This article presents the results of the Top Trends survey 2021. The raw data for the survey can be found in the data appendix at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4530743>.

A total of 94 facilities responded to the survey – up from 66 in 2020 and 38 in 2019.

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Summary

Overall, the results of the survey show an enormous acceleration in the implementation of new projects in IT institutions. Many institutions expect this trend to continue even after the end of the pandemic. The responses reveal a clear tension between the rapid provision of new services from the cloud, the compliance requirements of data protection and information security, and the resource requirements for on-site operations. In previous years, such strategic deliberations on sourcing and operational architecture were hardly addressed. However, in this year's survey responses, these aspects are mentioned in almost all question categories.

The top trends in 2021 for the ZKI community are the topics:

Figure 1: Relevant top trends and number of mentions

The survey asks on the one hand about general IT trends and on the other hand about trends that are particularly relevant for one's own institution (cf. Fig. 1). Among the general top trends, the topics "cloud", "digitalisation" and "information security" are the top mentions – followed by "machine learning" and the topics "mobile working" and "digital sovereignty". The top trends that are particularly relevant for IT institutions are mostly identical, except for the topic of "machine learning", which generally appears in fourth place as a trend, but only in eleventh place among the topics in terms of relevance for their own institution. Instead, the topics "data protection" and "collaboration solutions" are also mentioned. "Digital sovereignty", "mobile working" and "collaboration solutions" have not been mentioned as a trend in any of the ZKI Top Trends surveys before and can therefore also be seen as direct effects of the pandemic. Particularly in the context of the Schrems II ruling, "digital sovereignty" is understood to mean complete reassessments of fundamental strategies of IT institutions for the portfolio, procurement, configuration, compliance and operation.

As in the previous years' results, the structures of IT governance are diverse with regard to different models, with almost one third of the institutions not having a CIO model in place. However, it is clear that the larger the institution, the more established the corresponding structures are. Only one institution with more than 30,000 students reports that it has not established a CIO model. The "CIO committee" structure is more common at universities. Only one university of applied sciences relies on this type of IT governance.

Most higher education institutions have extensively expanded the systems for online teaching and established new services. The IT facilities have taken on much more extensive tasks than before, especially in the areas of support and communication.

The rapid expansion of services and scaling has brought information security and data protection even further into focus. This has also led to improved cooperation with these areas.

The increased interest in the services is also accompanied by a higher expectation of the quality of the services and a closer exchange with the users. These effects have led to a clear dynamisation of digitisation at the institutions. The extensive ad-hoc digitalisations could already be consolidated in approx. 37% of the institutions.

Most institutions, on the other hand, report no or only minor effects of the pandemic on research IT. In some cases, higher demand is cited in the areas of research data management, HPC and machine learning.

The services for working from home were expanded and new hardware, especially notebooks, was procured. In some cases, new architecture and security concepts were developed for mobile working. Due to the increased effort for training and support, personnel bottlenecks in these areas have become more visible. Overall, it is emphasised that home office works well – even in areas where it previously seemed unthinkable.

Through online collaboration, the interaction between employees has changed in a predominantly positive way. They report more communication, more efficient meetings, more creativity, fewer concerns and more structured project management. On the other hand, leadership and management are described as more time-consuming and difficult.

In addition to the many services to be established and expanded, the ECJ ruling Schrems II has brought about significant changes. Institutions are reviewing their own services in this regard, reassessing and describing fundamental implications for sourcing and operational strategies. In this context, a significant increase in the workload for coordinating security concepts and data processing agreements is reported, as well as a professionalisation of processes.

Regarding videoconferencing services, most institutions report operating two or more videoconferencing systems for different scenarios. The strategy for these systems will be re-evaluated in many institutions after the pandemic.

Questions about the participating institutions

The following diagrams give an overview of the type and size of the institutions as well as the roles of the participating persons.

Figure 2: Type of institution of survey participants; n=91

Figure 3: Number of students at the survey participants' institution; n=88

Figure 4: Role of survey participants in the university; n=83

Not all participants indicated where their institution is located. The 72 locations mentioned are distributed among the federal states as follows.

Figure 5: Distribution of survey participants among the federal states; n=72

IT Governance

The next question refers to the IT governance model established in the respective institution.

Figure 6: Model of IT governance at own institution; n=81

The increased number of responses in 2021 will make it possible to better investigate in which form of higher education and at which size of institution the models are preferred in each case.

Figure 7: IT governance to size grouped by governance model; n=81

Figure 8: IT governance grouped by size of institution; n=81

The following figures show the model of IT governance in relation to the type of institution.

Figure 9: IT governance by university type; n=81

Due to the higher number of responses, the distribution of governance models in the federal states can also be shown for the year 2021.

Figure 10: IT governance in the federal states; n=61

Focus 2021: Impact of the pandemic on IT facilities

For the year 2021, the question focus was placed on the impact of the pandemic on IT facilities.

What impact has there been on teaching services and technologies?

There were 48 responses to this question.

Most universities have extensively expanded their own systems for online teaching. Not only have many new services been put into operation, but existing services have also been scaled and expanded for much greater use. Video conferencing systems are mentioned most frequently. Mentioned by name are the solutions BigBlueButton, Flowcast, Jitsi, Microsoft Teams, Matrix, Nextcloud Talk, OnlyOffice, OpenCast Studio, Overleaf, RocketChat, Seafile, Cisco WebEx and Zoom.

The effort for support and communication has increased considerably for the IT institutions. Examples mentioned in this context are the intensified exchange on data protection and IT security issues as well as generally broader discussions on services and the suitability of platforms. The increased use of services is also accompanied by increased demands on the quality of service provision. This is based on a considerably increased interest of users in new solutions and the desire to be involved in the selection and design of services.

Completely new services were developed for contact tracing¹ in presence and hybrid mode, whereby the universities are pursuing very different approaches to implementation.

Furthermore, collaboration solutions, services for online examinations and video recordings are mentioned.

Overall, a clear dynamisation of digitisation at the institutions and high time pressure overall are reported, which has also led to a considerable additional workload for staff at the IT institutions.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Scaling of the services	15
Online teaching	14
Video conferencing systems	10
Many new services	8
More support and communication	7
Dynamisation of digitalisation	6
Contact tracing	4
Burdens for staff	3
Digital collaboration	3
Services for online examinations	3
Lecture recording	3

What was the impact on services for research IT?

There were 40 responses to this question.

The majority of responses report little or no impact on research IT, as the focus of the impact of the pandemic – according to survey responses – is more on teaching. However, the provision of secure access from outside the HEIs and more support activities are mentioned. Some HEIs also report an increase in requests for research data management, high performance computing and machine learning. There are also isolated reports of needs for support for digital events and special

¹ See also Dreyer, Malte, & Hotzel, Hartmut. (2020). Survey on contact tracing. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4045311>

collaboration solutions. Jitsi, Nextcloud, OnlyOffice and Cisco WebEx are cited as newly provided services in this context.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Little to none	22
Secure remote access	3
More support	2
Services for collaboration	2

What impact has there been in terms of working from home?

There were 45 responses to this question.

The focus of the impact was on the procurement of hardware, notebooks and other devices for use from home. To enable the increased access from outside the university, VPN capacities were expanded at many universities. In general, capacities, licences and information offers for the services used in the home office were also massively increased. In some cases, completely new architecture and security concepts for working in the home office and for mobile working in general have been created and implemented in order to be able to access the administrative systems more flexibly.² In this context, security issues for access to data with high protection requirement and open questions for access through private devices as well as missing service agreements to work from home are described.

Due to the scope of the measures and the amount of hardware procured, the workload of the IT facilities for training and support has increased a lot. Here, staff bottlenecks have become more visible than in times of lower workload. Many processes have been switched to online procedures. However, it is emphasised that home office works well – even in areas where it was previously unthinkable.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Training and support	9
VPN expansion	8
Procurement of notebooks	6
Notebook output	5
More workplaces in the home office	4
Hardware procurement	3
Devices for the home office are missing	3
Many new services	3
Zoom	3

² See also Dreyer, Malte. (2020). Brief survey on the situation of digital offerings for teaching and home office in April 2020 <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3826557>

What has changed in the interaction of the employees in your institution?

There were 43 responses to this question.

The answers to this question are partly contradictory. The majority describe more and better communication, better cooperation, shorter distances and an improvement in the meeting culture or more concentrated meetings. In addition to video conferencing as a basis, the use of other tools and methods for project management is generally cited as a necessary condition for success, with open source solutions gaining more recognition than before the pandemic. More meetings, more emails, communication via chats as well as more creativity and ad-hoc communication are mentioned as answers together with fewer concerns and a great commitment of the employees. Digital systems are also described as operational for conducting interviews, with the induction of new employees in particular being mentioned as a particular problem area and challenge when contact is purely digital. In this context, the use of digital tools is described as a matter of course and as an elementary step towards digitalisation.

On the other hand, individual responses report more effort for leadership and coordination, longer coordination paths and a general slowdown. Leadership is generally perceived as more difficult in some responses and a tendency to dissolve boundaries in communication is named as a problem. In addition, it is noted that the initially stronger cooperation has decreased again in the course of the pandemic. Other negative effects mentioned by participants in the survey include less spontaneous communication, fewer breaks, more difficult communication and a lack of short conversations around personal meetings.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
More digital communication	11
More meetings	7
Cooperation has improved	6
More ad-hoc communication	5
Processes were accelerated	3
Induction of new employees is more difficult	2
More project management	2
Leap into digitalisation	2
Interpersonal issues fade into the background	2

Could the ad-hoc digitalisations be consolidated?

There were 46 responses to this question.

37% of the ad-hoc digitisation measures have already been made permanent. A further 37% of the responses indicate partial consolidation and 26% report that the measures have not yet been consolidated in any way.

For the partial continuations, restrictions on teaching or the purely technical aspects such as the financing of licences or IT systems are mentioned. For the area of staffing support for services, the survey responses cite more difficult funding for additional staff and the general shortage of IT staff in the labour market, which has even increased since the pandemic.

Some responses describe an analysis of the measures planned for 2021 or for the time after the pandemic, which should precede the continuation considerations and in which the changed framework conditions – such as higher security requirements, questions of digital sovereignty or lower online portions for teaching in regular operation – will also be included in the evaluation. In this regard, many responses assume that the working conditions will have changed permanently after the pandemic and that there will therefore no longer be a return to the previous forms of work.

Figure 11: Continuation of ad-hoc digitisation; n=46

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Yes	16
No	11
Partial	10
No additional staff	3
Teaching area only	3
Technical only	2

How do you deal with the ECJ ruling Schrems II? What effects does the ruling have on you?

There were 45 responses to this question.

The answers vary greatly. Seven respondents say they see no impact from the ruling. Others describe the review of all software and services used as well as the search for alternatives, negotiations with providers and a tendency to avoid products from US providers. In addition to increased operation of software solutions locally, greater consideration of the impact of the ruling in strategic considerations is also described as a consequence. Some survey participants state that new contracts will only be concluded with European companies or that non-EU cloud solutions should be avoided. The feedback mentions more attention to a data-saving configuration, stricter organisational terms of use, the pseudonymisation of mail addresses, more additional security measures and the prohibition of public clouds for sensitive data as further measures. In addition, a stronger focus on the alignment of data processing agreements, security concepts and further contractual terms is cited as another consequence. In this context, cooperation with local data protection authorities is described as intensified and improved.

A coordinated approach to dealing with the new situation is reported from the state of Baden-Württemberg.

Due to the additional measures, a significantly higher effort for the introduction of new services is described. On the other hand, no response mentions the shutdown of existing services due to the ruling.

Furthermore, higher education management is said to be more aware of data protection issues and the framework conditions for the use of software solutions as a result of the ruling.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Major uncertainties	7
No effects	7
Negotiations with suppliers	6
Joint action in the federal state	5
More coordination with data protection	4
More operation on site	3
Search and procurement of alternative products	3
Review of all services	3
Impact on strategic considerations	2
Gradually adapt existing contracts	2
Increased effort for the introduction of systems	2
Use of the standard contractual clauses	2
Testing of all systems	2
Renunciation of non-EU cloud solutions	2

What is your strategy regarding video conferencing solutions?

There were 51 responses to this question.

Video conferencing technologies are the central building block for communication during the pandemic³. Most participants report having or planning to use two or more systems for video conferencing – often with one solution of these in on-site operation.

Several feedbacks emphasise wanting to re-evaluate the strategy for video conferencing solutions after the end of the pandemic. Reasons given for several systems include problems with large conferences, lack of acceptance for non-commercial systems, security classifications for sensitive communication processes and the trustworthiness of systems. End-to-end encryption and pseudonymisation of user data are cited as measures to maintain the operation of US providers. Some survey participants report an increase in requirements due to hybrid scenarios and specific needs from teaching, which necessitates a re-evaluation of the products used. The changed requirements are to be collected through surveys of university members.

Initiatives to acquire joint licences or to set up a state-wide cloud solution for videoconferencing are mentioned by some federal states. Other responses report an expectation from the DFN association to provide a suitable solution for all universities.

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Two systems in use	21
More operation on site	6
Multiple systems	5
Security classification for videoconferencing	4
Reassessment after the end of the pandemic	3
BigBlueButton and commercial solution	2
Search for an integrated solution for everything	2

³ See also Dreyer, Malte. (2020). Survey on Digital Teaching Offerings at Universities in June 2020
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3925120>

Changes in the top trends compared to the previous year

These questions are intended to shed light on how the top trends relevant to IT institutions change over the years at universities and research institutions.

Compared to the previous year 2020, the top trends have changed as follows:

Figure 12: Change in relevance; n=89

For the topics that are mentioned in the top trends in several years, the following changes occur over the years:

Trend	Place in the Top Trends			
	2021	2020	2019	2018
Information security	2	1	2	5
Digitisation	3	3	6	1
Cloud	1	2	6	4
Research Data Management	10	7	3	2
Machine learning	11	4	5	
Cooperations	8	5	4	7
Staff	9	6	9	
Virtualisation		9		9
Data protection	4		3	

It becomes clear that the top trends "information security", "digitalisation" and "cloud" were each represented in the top three rankings in recent years – but with a slightly different order.

From the following illustration, it is clearer how the topics change in rank within the top trends between 2018 and 2021:

Figure 13: Ranking of the top trends between 2018 and 2021

Here, a lower number is to be understood as a higher ranking in the Top Trend, such as rank "1" with a higher relevance than rank "2".

Evaluating the top trends in 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 together, the following ranking over four years emerges.

Top Trend	Place
Information security	1
Cloud	2
Digitisation	3
Research Data Management	4
Cooperations	5
Data protection	6
Machine learning	7
Staff	8
Long-term archiving	9
Big Data	10
Virtualisation	11
Micro-Services	12
Outsourcing	13
Process management	14
Agile organisation	15
E-bill	16
Centralisation	17

The top trends "information security", "digitalisation" and "cloud" are also the top mentions over several years.

For individual topics, a more specific progression of the assessment of relevance over the years can be given.

The importance of the topic "information security" continues to increase.

Figure 14: Assessment of the change in relevance of information security over the years

For the topic of "Cloud", there was a significant increase in importance in the course of 2020, presumably also due to the pandemic, which is also reflected in the number 1 position within the top trends for the year 2021.

Figure 15: Assessment of the change in relevance of cloud technologies over the years

The relevance of the topic of "digitalisation" continues to increase.

Figure 16: Assessment of the change in the relevance of digitalisation over the years

The topic of "cooperations" is a trend that has been mentioned relatively consistently over the years. Since 2018, the trend has had slightly lower mentions in the area of increasing relevance for the following year.

Figure 17: Assessment of the change in the relevance of cooperations over the years

The topic of research data management continues to receive frequent mentions, but has received slightly lower mentions in the area of increasing relevance for the following year in each case since 2018.

Figure 18: Assessment of the change in relevance of research data management over the years

Results of the core survey

In each year, 12 constant questions are asked in the survey, which are answered as free text. From these texts, thematic circles are derived and normalised, which are then grouped for this list.

What top trends do you see in the IT sector in general?

The general top trends in 2021 with at least three mentions are:

Place	Most frequent mentions	Frequency
1	Cloud	17
2	Digitisation	15
3	Information security	15
4	Machine Learning	10
5	Mobile working	8
6	Digital sovereignty	7
7	Data protection	5
8	Skills shortage	4
9	Research data	3
10	Cooperations	3

Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?

The relevant top trends in 2021 with at least three mentions are:

Place	Most frequent mentions	Frequency
1	Cloud	13
2	Information security	13
3	Digitisation	10
4	Data protection	5
5	Digital sovereignty	5
6	Mobile working	5
7	Collaboration solutions	4
8	Cooperations	4
9	Staff shortage	4
10	Research data	3
11	Machine Learning	3

Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant in the coming year?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
GDPR	17
Online Access Act	12
E-Government Act	7
Schrems II	6
BITV 2.0	2
ePrivacy Regulation	2
TV-L Annex A Grouping IT	2
Public procurement law	2

Which topics are you currently working on strategically?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Information security	10
Digitisation	8
Digitalisation strategy	5
Staff	5
IT Governance	4
Cooperation structures	4
Research data	3
E-learning	2
Green IT	2
Identity management	2
IT Service Portfolio Management	2
IT controlling	2
IT strategy	2
Mobile working	2
Structural planning	2
Ratio IT Central / Decentralised	2
Centralisation of IT	2

What new management tasks are you currently working on?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Staff	4
Personnel planning	4
Digitisation	3
IT Governance	3
Project management	3
IT Service Management	2
Communication	2
Process management	2
Structure Service Desk	2

In which area are external services becoming more important for you?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Cloud	10
Information security	9
Consulting	6
Video conferencing solutions	4
Campus management system	2
In all areas	2
IT Law	2
SaaS	2
Support during weekend	2
Maintenance and service	2

In which areas are you investing more than before?

The nominations in 2021 with at least two nominations are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Information security	10
Cloud / SaaS	6
Staff	6
Video conferencing	6
Network expansion	5
Online collaboration tools	5
Digitisation	4
Software licences	4
Advice and service	3
Teaching and learning platforms	3
Media technology	3
Mobile workstations	3
External service providers	2
Research data	2
Streaming offers	2

Which technologies are becoming more important for you?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Cloud	15
Container	4
Virtualisation	4
Multifactor authentication	3
Video conferencing systems	3
IaaS	2
Collaboration solutions	2
Open Source	2

What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
DMS	7
Collaboration platform	5
M365	3
Applicant management	2
HISinOne	2
Video conferencing	2

What skills would you like to build in your organisation over the next year?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
More awareness for data protection and information security	5
More knowledge about cloud technologies	5
Better service and support	4
Project management	4
Service Management	4
Agility	3
Better communication	2
IT architecture	2
IT center as business partner	2

Which staff skills are becoming more important?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Communication skills	12
Team orientation	7
Agile project management	4
Information security and data protection	4
Process analyses	4
Networked thinking	4
Flexibility	3
Project work	3
Independent work	3
Adaptation of cloud solutions	2
IT Service Management	2
Willingness to learn	2
Infrastructure management	2

Which staff skills are becoming less important?

The responses in 2021 with at least two mentions are:

Most frequent mentions	Frequency
Solving everything alone	4
Specialists	3
Administration	2
Hardware knowledge	2
None	2
Programming skills	2

Directories

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List of questions

1. Basic questions
 - What type of university do you come from?
 - University
 - University of Applied Sciences
 - Art / Music College
 - Church university
 - Dual university
 - State-recognised private university
 - Research facility
 - Other
 - No answer
 - What is your role in the organisation?
 - CIO
 - Head of an IT facility (computer centre)
 - Head of another central institution
 - Other:
 - no answer
 - In which city is your institution located?
 - How many students does your university have?
 - Up to 5,000
 - 5,001 to 15,000
 - 15,001 to 30,000
 - More than 30,000
 - Comment
 - No answer
2. Which organisational model for IT governance is used at your university?
 - Chancellor or Vice President / as CIO
 - CIO with staff function in the Presidential Staff
 - Head of a central IT facility as CIO
3. Changes compared to previous year
 - Please indicate whether, in your view, the relevance of the topic has increased, decreased or not changed since last year.
4. Focus topic: Impact of the pandemic on IT institutions
 - What impact has there been on teaching services and technologies?
 - What was the impact on services for research IT?
 - What impact has there been in terms of home office support?
 - What has changed in the interaction of the employees in your institution?
 - Could the ad-hoc digitalisations be consolidated?
 - How do you deal with the ECJ ruling Schrems II? What effects does the ruling have on you?
 - What is your strategy regarding video conferencing solutions?
5. Core survey
 - What top trends do you see in the IT sector in general?
 - Which top trends are particularly relevant for you?
 - Which legislative regulations do you see as particularly relevant for you in the coming year?
 - Which topics are you currently working on strategically?
 - What new management tasks are you currently working on?

- In which area are external services becoming more important for you?
- In which areas are you investing more than before?
- Which technologies are becoming more important for you?
- What new services or technologies are you currently introducing?
- What IT skills would you like to build in your organisation in the next year?
- Which staff skills are becoming more important?
- Which staff skills are becoming less important?

Surveys from previous years

2020

Survey

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666168>

Data attachment

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666170>

2019

Survey

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590659>

Data attachment

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590683>

2018

Survey

<https://zenodo.org/record/1196427>

Data attachment

<https://zenodo.org/record/1183499>